

TUoDX Conference: Decision Support Systems and Sustainable Competitive Advantage During a Disruptive Event

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ABSTRACT

In a rapidly changing business environment due to COVID-19, a decision support system can assist firms in the decision making process. The purpose of this paper is to study the effect of decision support systems (DSS) on sustainable competitive advantage through the mediator agility, during a disruptive event. Prior research has established a link between these variables, however not in the context of a disruptive event. By referring to this past research, and performing a survey on firms within the manufacturing industry in the Netherlands, the results of the regression analysis indicate that only the relationship between agility and sustainable competitive advantage is significant. This preliminary research gives direction to further research.

Keywords

Decision support systems, business agility, sustainable competitive advantage, disruptive events.

INTRODUCTION

In the current COVID-19 pandemic, different industries are drastically changing. For example, according to an ING report, COVID-19 yielded a negative impact on the Dutch manufacturing industry. Both production and demand have been heavily impacted (ING, 2020). Furthermore, producer confidence in the Netherlands has had a major decline since the start of the pandemic. Although there have been some improvements with a slow increase in confidence in recent months, it is still a negative indicator (CBS, 2020).

Therefore, the capability to adapt (agility) to

the changing environments is a key competence to keep performing as an organization (Ravichandran, 2018). Numerous firms use decision support systems (DSS) to help make the right decision. By making this process quicker, it will result in a business that could adapt more easily to changes. This is important in a situation where the external environment of a firm is changing drastically. DSS can support the decision making process in drastic changing environments such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

A DSS is a form of Business Intelligence & Analytics that can be defined as interactive computer based systems and subsystems intended to help decision makers use communication technologies, data, documents, knowledge and models to complete decision process tasks (Holsapple & Whinston, 1996). Information that a decision support application might gather and present would be accessing all information assets, including; legacy and relational data sources, comparative data figures, projected figures based on new data or assumptions, and consequences of different decision alternatives given past experience in a specific context (Power, 2002).

Academic research consistently demonstrates a relationship between a DSS and achieving a higher level of sustainable competitive advantage (SCA) (Gowen and Tallon, 2005; Barney, 1991). SCA is a value-creating strategy that is not simultaneously implemented by current or potential competitors, and when these competitors are not capable of duplicating the benefits of this strategy (Barney, 1991). However, the relationship between DSS and SCA during a disruptive event is not entirely clear and calls for further research.

The study will contribute to the literature by proposing a new way to understand how a DSS relates to a SCA during a disruptive event. The result

of this empirical study is a new way to understand the relationship between business agility that is driven by a DSS and the effect on the SCA of a manufacturing firm in the Netherlands during a disruptive event such as COVID-19, on which future research can be built.

A survey is conducted from a small sample from the target group by which the data collection method will be validated. To increase the generalizability of the results of the research, we focus on a specific branch; firms within the manufacturing industry in the Netherlands. As the impact of COVID-19 has been negative on the manufacturing industry it would be interesting to conduct research whether a DSS can have a positive impact. Furthermore, this ensures that the results can be properly generalized back to the population.

In addition, Lee et al. (2008) and Sambamurthy et al. (2003) have established the effect of business agility on creating a SCA, and Strohmaier & Rollet (2005) the extent on how decision support systems positively influence business agility. Several studies have provided information and knowledge on how to handle and act during a disruptive event (Chen et al., 2014). However, a combination of these two views only has limited information about the earlier stated relationships during a disruptive event. Therefore, this paper will focus on the combination of business agility, driven by decision support systems and the effect on SCA during a disruptive event such as COVID-19 by answering the following research question:

“To what extent does business agility relate to a higher level of sustainable competitive advantage when operating in times of a disruptive event, and what effect does a decision support system have on business agility?”

To answer this research question, we formulate the following sub-research questions:

Theoretical research questions:

1. *What is a decision support system?*
2. *What is sustainable competitive advantage?*
3. *How does decision support systems relate to business agility?*
4. *How does the relationship between a decision support system and sustainable competitive advantage differ when operating during or without a disruptive event?*

Practical research questions:

1. *To what extent is a disruptive event related to sustainable competitive advantage?*

2. *To what extent are decision support systems related to business agility?*

THEORY

Researchers should take into account the proper construct definition and provide a clear conceptual definition for their proposed research constructs in order to convey the meaning of their theory (Rivard, 2014). Therefore, the conceptual framework of the current study begins with a definition of each related construct and issues.

Degree of integration of the Decision Support System

For the purpose of this paper, a decision support system is defined as an interactive computer based systems and subsystems intended to help decision makers use communication technologies, data, documents, knowledge and models to complete decision process tasks (Holsapple & Whinston, 1996).

Firms attempt to capture the required information and analyze it to prepare analytical insights for decision-makers (Nam et al., 2019). These insights can be used for three different types of business decision making: Strategic (long range plans; 2-5 years), Tactical (short range plans; 0-2 years) and Operational (shortest range plans; a few days) (Davis, 1979).

Firms have to be able to adapt to external factors in a quick manner to survive. Through making the right decision fast on the tactical and especially on operational level, a firm could adapt to the changing external factors.

Information systems have both descriptive and normative components. The degree of integration of those components are important to determine the effectiveness of a DSS on the business agility. An information system has to be deeply integrated in the firm in order to help decision makers make decisions effectively and in an agile way (Strohmaier & Rollett, 2005; Petter et al., 2008). The desirable characteristics of the degree of integration of a DSS are: responsiveness, relevance, understandability, conciseness, accuracy, reliability, completeness and usability (Petter et al., 2008).

Two factors are important to make the right decision at a quick pace (Ashrafi et al., 2019):

- Information quality is the basis for effective decision-making
- Innovative capabilities are of importance to put innovative ideas into practice.

A DSS can positively influence the information quality in a firm if it is designed for the right purpose (Nada et al., 2014). In addition, a firm has to offer innovative capabilities otherwise adapting to certain external changes can be difficult (Ravichandran, 2018).

A DSS can improve the distribution of quality information of a firm. And in combination with innovation capabilities, DSS will have a positive impact on business agility (Ashrafi et al., 2019). Overby et al. (2006) supports this statement, by concluding that IT, and therefore a DSS, increases business agility. The purpose of this research is to gain more understanding of the effect of using a well integrated DSS on the SCA of a production firm through business agility. That is why the focus is on the information quality of a DSS system.

Therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: The degree of integration of the DSS positively influences business agility.

Business Agility

Business agility is defined as the firm's ability to sense opportunities for competitive action and gather the resources to seize those market opportunities (Goldman et al., 1994). Agility includes the ability to identify and implement these opportunities, quickly accurately, and cost efficiently. This consists of (1) innovational agility that creates, new products, services or business models, and (2) the resilience agility, where the firm is adaptive to threats and challenges arising from regulatory or environmental changes, changes in technology, and consumer behavior (Overby et al., 2006; Sambamurthy et al., 2003).

Lee et al. (2008) distinguishes between two different types of agility: entrepreneurial and adaptive agility. Entrepreneurial agility refers to the ability to create new business models by which a competitive advantage can be achieved. This business model can imply a new product, service, and/or a business process, that is revolutionary in nature.

Adaptive agility is the ability to launch actions to keep pace with the market and industry, or be resilient to changes in business environments. Prior organizational-research defines resilience as the organization's capability to manage disruptions and unexpected events to shorten unfavorable aftermaths and maximize the organization's speed of recovery to the original or to a new more desirable state (Annarelli & Nonino, 2016). The study of Lee et al. (2008) and Sambamurthy et al. (2003) establish a link between business agility and SCA. Therefore we propose the following hypothesis:

H2: Business agility positively influences achieving a sustainable competitive advantage

Sustainable Competitive Advantage

Sustainable competitive advantage (SCA) can be defined as an implemented value-creating strategy that is not simultaneously implemented by current or potential competitors, and when these competitors are not capable of duplicating the benefits of this strategy (Barney, 1991). The *sustainable* characteristic does not depend on the period of time, but on the possibility of duplication by competitors (Nadarajah et al., 2014). According to Barney (1991) who has based his research on several theories of Michael Porter (Porter, 1985), the competitive advantage must therefore still exist, even after the efforts of competitors to duplicate that advantage have failed. This characteristic differentiates SCA from competitive advantage (CA), as Barney (1991) defines CA as an implemented value-creating strategy that is not simultaneously implemented by current or potential competitors. Nevertheless, the aforementioned characteristic does not imply that SCA will last forever. Due to unanticipated changes in the economic structure of an industry, it may be that what was once a resource of SCA is no longer of value to a firm, and therefore no longer a resource of any CA (Barney, 1991).

SCA's value-creating strategy can be accomplished by specific firm resources. Barney (1991) defines firm resources as "*all assets, capabilities, organizational processes, firm attributes, information, knowledge, etc. controlled by a firm that enable the firm to conceive of and implement strategies that improve its efficiency and effectiveness*". These resources must satisfy four key attributes, namely value, rareness, inimitability and non-substitutability (Nadarajah et al., 2014; Wade & Hulland, 2004). The attribute *value* implies that the resource enables a firm to conceive or implement strategies that improve the firm's efficiency and effectiveness. *Rareness* refers to the ability to create uniqueness that distinguishes the organization from competitors. Subsequently, *inimitability* is the ability to create value that is difficult for competitors to duplicate. The difficulty may be due to high investment costs, complexity or know-how. Finally, *non-substitutability* is where competitors are unable to replace the resource with another equivalent (Barney, 1991; Wade & Hulland, 2004). CA is already achieved when a firm possesses resources that are valuable and rare, while SCA arises from resources that are also inimitable and non-substitutable (Barney, 1991).

Resource-based View & Relationship between integration DSS and SCA

A firm resource must satisfy all four key attributes to hold the potential of SCA. These four key attributes can be used as empirical indicators of how heterogeneous and immobile a firm's resources are and hence how useful these resources are for creating SCA (Barney, 1991). Heterogeneous means that firms can have different strategies because they possess different resources (Barney, 1991), and immobility is about the tradability limitations and imitability limitations of resources (Andersén, J., Jansson, C., & Ljungkvist, T., 2016). Barney (1991) has constructed a model for this, called the Resource-based View (RBV) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The Relationship Between Resource Heterogeneity and Immobility, Value, Rareness, Imperfect Imitability, and Substitutability, and Sustained Competitive Advantage (Barney, 1991)

Barney (1991) argues that based on his RBV, an information processing system used for informal and formal management decision-making processes that allows a firm to consider large amounts of data quickly and share this data efficiently, may hold the potential of SCA because it is rare and inimitable. However, an information processing system of that kind can be substituted. But that does not directly mean that a firm resource cannot be a source of SCA (Barney, 1991).

Holsapple and Whinston (1996) state that DSS are intended to help decision makers use a certain resource to complete decision process tasks. The DSS focusses on a certain type of resource, called a driven DSS. The DSS can be communications driven, data driven, document driven, knowledge driven or model driven. Because the definition of an information processing system, given by Barney (1991), complies with a communications driven and a knowledge driven DSS, there can be said that based on the RBV, certain types of DSS have a direct positive influence on the SCA of a firm. A communications driven DSS provides various technologies such as video conferencing, to support internal teams working on a shared task who have to make decisions to establish a solution or strategy. A knowledge driven DSS is mainly used to provide management advice. This type of DSS can suggest or recommend actions to managers (Marin, 2008).

With the RBV, Barney (1991) proves there is a definite relationship between DSS and SCA. We go a step beyond this, and consider how this relationship behaves when the mediator 'Business agility' comes into play.

Level of disruption

The environment surrounding organizations increasingly challenges them by posing different threats in various forms from both inside and outside an enterprise's boundaries (Annarelli & Nonino, 2016). Natural disasters, pandemic disease, terrorist attacks, economic recession, equipment failure and human errors are only some examples that help in understanding how many different events can undermine the stability and security of an organization and its environment (Bhamra et al., 2011). Disasters are a multivarious concept composed of many different elements that seem to defy any precise definition (Alexander 2003).

The conceptualization of environmental turbulence encompasses changes in competitors' actions, customers' preferences, product / service life cycle length, regulatory or legal changes, economical or technical shifts (e.g., Chakravarty et al. 2013; Overby et al. 2006; Pavlou and El Sawy 2010) as well as internal changes or crises (Pavlou and El Sawy 2010).

Turbulence refers to the volatility or difficult-to-predict discontinuities in an environment. (Dess & Beard, 1984; Eisenhardt, 1989; Emery & Trist, 1965; Haleblian & Finikelstein, 1993; Keats & Hitt, 1988)

We do not differentiate the level of disruption further, but we use the general notion that a pandemic disease can undermine the stability & security of an organization and its environment (Bhamra et al., 2011). Therefore, we look through the lens of COVID-19 and the relation towards achieving a SCA considering business agility. We propose the following hypotheses:

H3: The level of disruption influences the relationship between business agility and achieving a sustainable competitive advantage.

H4: The level of disruption influences achieving a sustainable competitive advantage.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

Based on the above arguments, we analyse the relationship (Gowen & Tallon, 2005) between the degree of integration of a decision support system (Ravichandran, 2018) and achieving a SCA (Barney, 1991) by considering business agility (Lee et al., 2008 and Sambamurthy et al., 2003) and the level of disruption (Bhamra et al., 2011) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Conceptual Model

METHOD

Method: The research started with searching for literature and research papers in the theme of Business Intelligence and Analytics. The research papers were mainly obtained from different business and Information management journals with a good reputation such as MIS Quarterly. These papers are used to form a strong theoretical basis and well-substantiated hypotheses for this research.

The purpose of this research is to gain more understanding of the effect of decision support systems on SCA in manufacturing firms in the Netherlands during a disruptive event. Therefore a field survey was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic to collect quantitative data for the purpose of testing the hypothesized relationships. A field survey is a good strategy to collect the insights and experiences with a population-based sample in a non-artificial setting. There is no other method that can do this (Krosnick, 1999).

Sample: Convenience sampling is used to select the participants for the survey because of the lacking amount of time and budget. The survey is sent to employees of manufacturing firms in the Netherlands within the reach of our own network. Because there are 21 parameters to measure the different variables, the sample size needs to be at least 210 respondents, because the sample size must be at least 10 times the number of parameters. Assuming a response rate of 10%, at least 2100 people need to be approached (Jackson, 2003).

Measurement: In the survey (appendix 1) there are 36 questions, of which 2 are open ended questions and the rest are likert scale and semantic differential questions, which use indicators based on peer-reviewed studies (mentioned in appendix 1).

The first 2 questions are about the identity of the firm that is filling in the survey. This helps with determining if the participant comes from a production firm. The survey is conducted during the period of November 16 and December 7 (3 weeks) via the online survey service of Google. This survey is then sent via email to individuals in our own network that live in the Netherlands that are working in manufacturing firms (located in the Netherlands).

Data preparation: There is one question about the existence of a DSS in the manufacturing firm. If the participant gives the answer that there is no DSS, then these answers will be removed from the sample results because we want to make sure that we get the results from the right participants with the right firm characteristics to ensure the validity of this research.

Each participant gave answers to the closed-ended questions in the survey that have Likert-scale answer possibilities. The values in the Likert-scale are clustered to calculate the mean result and standard deviation per variable (Uma & Bougie, 2016).

Method of analysis: SPSS has been used to calculate the mean results. Furthermore, SPSS is used to perform a linear regression and multiple linear regression analysis. From this analysis, the ANOVA table can be used to determine the determination coefficient (R-SQUARED). The determination coefficient explains the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable. The sig. from the ANOVA table is used to determine the significance of the model. This will explain to what extent the model is explained by coincidence. The significance level has to be low to let the model be statistically significant. The linear regression is used to determine the relationship between the variables of degree of integration of a DSS and business agility since it is a regression between one independent variable and one dependent variable. The multiple linear regression is used to determine the relationship between the independent variables level of disruption and business agility and the dependent variable SCA. Business agility has an interaction term with level of disruption because the level of disruption moderates the relationship between business agility and SCA.

There is also the coefficients table that presents the direction coefficients of the model. The significance of each variable helps with interpreting the usefulness of the each direction coefficient (G. Nieuwenhuis, 2009).

Reliability: For multi-item measures, Cronbach's Alpha can be used to check whether the set of items are interrelated. For single item measures, Cronbach's Alpha cannot be checked. The value of Cronbach's alpha must be at least 0.7 to consider it as acceptable (Uma & Bougie, 2016).

But, as stated by Peterson (1994), the acceptable level of the alpha differs for different functions of research (i.e. preliminary, basic or, applied research). Because this is a preliminary study of a basic research topic, a minimal level of 0.6 is needed (Nunnally, 1967). Every question that is used to measure the value of the variables have to be answered in a Likert scale form. The measurement attributes derive from high quality research papers that are peer reviewed on the subject of Business intelligence and Analytics. To minimize missing data in different constructs we used the option in Google forms to make every question mandatory to fill in.

Validity: DSS has been measured in past research based on established scales by Petter et al., (2008). Whose measures have been found to be valid in a vast amount of prior research. In addition, the measure of the mediator business agility has been used in prior research based on two dimensions and five indicators (Miller & Friesen, 1983; Ramanujan & Venkatraman, 1987; MacMillan, 1983; Sethi & King, 1994; Zahra & Covin, 1995; Hult et al., 2005; Tracey et al., 1999; Sheffi & Rice Jr., 2005; Subramani & Youndt, 2005; Jarrar & Zairi, 2000). The dependent variable, SCA, is a highly theoretical construct. However, the measurement of Barney (1991) has been widely used when measuring SCA. Finally, the quasi moderator *level of disruption*, which has been classified as the pandemic disease COVID-19, is an abstract measure. As such, a multi-item measure is used for this construct.

The overall external validity of this study may potentially be low. However, because of the specific branch and country chosen for this survey, we try to increase generalizability. The setting on how the sample is created is convenience sampling. Hence, the generalizability cannot be automatically generalized to the entire manufacturing industry.

RESULTS

To test the reliability of the scales used in the survey, Cronbach's Alphas are computed for each construct (and sub-dimension were available), as shown in Table 1. As stated by Peterson (1994), the acceptable level of the alpha differs for different functions of research (i.e. preliminary, basic or, applied research). Because this is a preliminary study of a basic research topic, a minimal level of 0.6 is needed (Nunnally, 1967). To keep the model parsimonious (i.e. to explain the most with the fewest variables), sub-dimensions are averaged in the final construct. Continuing, the Least Square Method (LSM) is used to describe the best fitting coefficients, see Table 2 and Table 3, respectively the mediation term from integration of DSS to agility, and the agility to SCA with the quasi

moderator level of disruption. This model has the following requirements: homoscedasticity, linearity, independence of the error terms, and normality, for this has been tested. The only requirement that is not met, is the normality of the residuals, even after transformation of the dependent variable, by transforming $\ln(Y)$, normality is not reached (Nieuwenhuis, 2009).

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study is to understand the relationships between business agility, that is driven by the degree of integration of the DSS, and the effect on the SCA of a manufacturing firm in the Netherlands during a disruptive event such as COVID-19. To ascertain this relationship, a regression analysis is used with the data from a field survey.

The results indicate that the degree of integration of the DSS is not significant enough to have an impact on business agility. One reason for that is the fact that R-SQUARED is not high enough (since it is close to 0) to make a statement about the business agility. In addition, the correlation coefficient of the linear regression model is not significant at a 10% significance level. Therefore, we are not able to reject the null hypothesis of H1.

Besides, the results show that business agility is important to create SCA for a manufacturing firm. The multiple linear regression model with the independent variables business agility and disruption level and the interaction term between the two explains 32,4% of the variation at a significance level of 10%. Therefore, this model is useful enough to conclude that a business being agile does have a significant effect on the SCA of a manufacturing firm. It is important to take into account that the only significant variable in this model is business agility (in contrast to the variables disruption level and the interaction term). Thus, we are able to reject the null hypothesis of H2, but we are not able to reject the null hypothesis H3 and H4.

This study makes several contributions to existing academic research. We established that there was limited to no prior research that empirically studies the relationships between business agility, driven by the degree of integration of a DSS, and SCA during a disruptive event. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to understand the relationships between business agility that is driven by the degree of integration of a DSS and the effect on the SCA of a manufacturing firm in the Netherlands during a disruptive event such as COVID-19. This paper contributes to research by proposing a new way to empirically study these relationships.

Table 1.*List of construct Cronbach's Alpha*

Construct	Sub-dimension	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Level of Disruption		2	0,802
Integration of DSS		6	0,634
Entrepreneurial Agility	Proactive	3	0,808
	Preemptive	2	0,724
	Radical	3	0,698
Adaptive Agility	Innovation		
	Reactive	2	0,615
	Incremental	3	0,751
Sustainable Competitive Advantage	Innovation	4	0,829

Table 2.*Model summary of Model 1: Integration of DSS on Agility*

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error		
1	(Constant)	2,156	1,456	1,481	0,161
	IDSS_C	0,352	0,362	0,971	0,348

Notes: Dependent Variable: AGI_C

F-test for model usefulness: ,348 (Predictors: IDSS_C)

R Square of model: 0,063

Table 3.*Model summary of Model 2: Agility on SCA with quasi moderator Level of Disruption*

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error		
2	(Constant)	-4,614	3,829	-1,205	0,251
	AGI_C	2,110	1,077	1,959	0,074
	DISR_AGI	-0,430	0,372	-1,157	0,270
	DISR_C	1,725	1,312	1,315	0,213

Notes: Dependent Variable: SCA_C

F-test for model usefulness: ,054 (Predictors: DISR_C, AGI_C, DISR_AGI)

Adjusted R Square of the model: 0,324

CONCLUSION

This research aims to provide insights into the relationship between business agility and the level of sustainable competitive advantage when operating in times of a disruptive event, and the effect of a decision support system on business agility.

Based on the results and discussion, there is carefully concluded that business agility has a significant effect on the sustainable competitive advantage of a manufacturing firm in the Netherlands. However, the effect of a decision support system on business agility cannot be concluded because of insignificance of the variable 'Degree of integration of decision support system' in the study. Similarly, the influence of a disruptive event on the relationship between business agility and achieving a sustainable competitive advantage, as well as its influence on achieving a sustainable competitive advantage cannot be concluded because of a too low significance value. One of the explanations for the low significance values is that the study has a relatively low number of respondents.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The research has several limitations. First, there may be other ways that DSS influences achieving a SCA. In addition, the measurement of level of disruption can be expended. Second, because of the cross-sectional nature of this study (the data required for the hypotheses was documented through the completion of a survey at one specific point in time), we are not able to completely understand the dynamics between the degree of integration of a DSS, business agility, level of disruption and a SCA over time. Last, we conducted the study only within one country (the Netherlands).

Due to the limited sample and relatively low response rate, the sample is not a true representation of the population.

Future research can increase the generalizability of the findings by examining cross-national or multinational surveys. Other countries can provide further insights based on differences between those countries. The hypotheses tested in the study represent only one moment in time, future research should consider longitudinal data, thus over time, in order to explore the dynamics between the degree of integration of a DSS, business agility, level of disruption and a SCA. In order to provide more rigorous findings. One final future improvement is the inclusion of control variables, such as the size of the firms or the number of employees. As that is not included in the study.

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APPENDIX 1: A CATEGORIZATION OF THE CONSTRUCTS

Variable	Dimension	Sub Dimension	Indicators	Source / own development
Level of disruption	Pandemic		Influence on production process	Own development
			Influence on supply chain	Own development
			Influence on sales	Own development
Degree of integration of DSS	Computer-based DSS		Existence	Own development
	Information use		Use of DSS in Decision making	(Davis, 1979)
	Information quality	DSS-process alignment	Responsiveness	(Petter et al., 2008)
		Quality of information output	Relevance	(Petter et al., 2008)
			Understandability	(Petter et al., 2008)
			Conciseness	(Petter et al., 2008)
			Reliability	(Petter et al., 2008)
			Completeness	(Petter et al., 2008)
			Usability	(Petter et al., 2008)
Business agility	Entrepreneurial Agility		Proactiveness	(Miller & Friesen, 1983) (Ramanujan & Venkatraman, 1987)
			Preemptiveness	(MacMillan, 1983) (Sethi & King, 1994)
			Radical Innovation	(Miller & Friesen, 1983) (Zahra & Covin, 1995)
	Adaptive Agility		Reactiveness	(Hult et al., 2005) (Tracey et al., 1999)
			Resilience	(Sheffi & Rice Jr., 2005)
			Incremental Innovation	(Subramani & Youndt, 2005) (Jarrar & Zairi, 2000)
Sustainable Competitive Advantage	Firm Resource, Heterogeneity & Firm Resource Immobility		Value, Rareness, Inimitability, non-substitutability	(Barney, 1991)

APPENDIX 2: THE SURVEY CONSTRUCTION

Variable	Indicators	Questions	Scale/measurement
Level of disruption	Influence on production process	To what extent did the COVID-19 pandemic influence the production process of your firm? (3 = neutral)	Semantic differential (1 = extremely negative, 5 = Extremely positive)
	Influence on supply chain	To what extent did the COVID-19 pandemic influence the supply chain of your firm? (3 = neutral)	Semantic differential (1 = extremely negative, 5 = Extremely positive)
	Influence on sales	To what extent did the COVID-19 pandemic influence the sales of your firm? (3 = neutral)	Semantic differential (1 = extremely negative, 5 = Extremely positive)
Degree of integration of DSS	Existence	Is there a computer program/application that helps you make decisions to perform tasks that are part of your job? (If you have selected 'I don't know' or 'No', then the form will be submitted.)	Yes, No or I don't know
	Use of DSS in Decision making	For what kind of decision making do you use this computer program/application? (Please mind that you can choose multiple answers.)	Strategic, Tactical, Operational and/or Other
	Responsive-ness	The program that you use to help make decisions does exactly what you want and when you want it.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
	Relevance	The information that you get from the computer program/application is relevant for the decisions that you have to make for your job.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
	Understand-ability	The information that you get from the computer program/application is understandable (te begrijpen).	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
	Conciseness	The information you get from the computer program/application is concise (beknopt) enough to help you make decisions.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
	Reliability	The information you get from the computer program/application is reliable (betrouwbaar) enough to help you make decisions.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
	Completeness	The information you get from the computer program/application is complete enough to help you make decisions.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)

APPENDIX 2: THE SURVEY CONSTRUCTION (CONTINUED)

	Usability	The information you get from the computer program/application is usable (bruikbaar) enough to help you to make decisions.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
Business agility	Proactiveness	Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to anticipate new business opportunities.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to seek new business opportunities.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to seek novel approaches to future market needs.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
	Preemptiveness	Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to be the first to market with new business approaches (or models).	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to develop new standards and practices in the industry.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to anticipate imitators through marketing actions.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
	Radical Innovation	Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to seek high-risk projects with chances of high return.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to support business experimentation despite uncertain returns.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to commit resources to radical changes that can potentially transform markets and competition.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)

APPENDIX 2: THE SURVEY CONSTRUCTION (CONTINUED)

	Usability	The information you get from the computer program/application is usable (bruikbaar) enough to help you to make decisions.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
Business agility	Proactiveness	Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to anticipate new business opportunities.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to seek new business opportunities.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to seek novel approaches to future market needs.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
	Preemptiveness	Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to be the first to market with new business approaches (or models).	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to develop new standards and practices in the industry.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to anticipate imitators through marketing actions.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
	Radical Innovation	Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to seek high-risk projects with chances of high return.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to support business experimentation despite uncertain returns.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to commit resources to radical changes that can potentially transform markets and competition.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)

APPENDIX 2: THE SURVEY CONSTRUCTION (CONTINUED)

	Reactiveness	Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to rapidly react to emerging opportunities in customer needs.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to rapidly react to emerging environmental opportunities. (e.g. new regulations, globalization)	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to rapidly react to emerging opportunities in markets.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
	Resilience	Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to rapidly respond to natural threats. (e.g. natural disaster)	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to rapidly respond to competitive threats. (e.g. competitor's price change and new marketing campaign)	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to rapidly respond to operational threats. (e.g. supply chain disruption)	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
	Incremental Innovation	Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to adapt existing business models. (e.g. grocery home delivery service)	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to adapt existing business processes. (e.g. self-scanning at supermarkets)	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)
		Relative to other firms in your industry, please indicate the ability of your firm to quickly adopt best practices used by others.	Likert scale (1 = Extremely weak, 5 = Extremely strong)

APPENDIX 2: THE SURVEY CONSTRUCTION (CONTINUED)

Sustainable Competitive Advantage	Value	Your firm resources satisfy the key attribute 'value'.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
	Rareness	Your firm resources satisfy the key attribute 'rareness'.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
	Inimitability	Your firm resources satisfy the key attribute 'inimitability'.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)
	Non-substitutability	Your firm resources satisfy the key attribute 'non-substitutability'.	Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree)